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REVIEW ARTICLE

Six Examples with Different Means of Operative Treatment of Humeral Shaft Fracture

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ABSTRACT

We showed different cases and operative treatment of traumatic fractures of humeral shaft including operative treatment by means of external fixation, intramedullary fixation with long humeral nailing, intramedullary fixation with Rush nail and plate osteosynthesis. The indications were chosen according to fracture anatomy and biology but foremost by specific socioeconomic comorbidities and aspects of the patient itself. Bone healing status, postoperative local status, neurocirculatory status, postoperative physical therapy course and overall functional results of injured limb and patient satisfaction.

Introduction

The humerus is the largest bone in the upper extremity. Midshaft humeral fractures account for about 2-5 % of all fractures [1,2]. They show bimodal distribution; the first peak is seen in the third decade in males and is associated with high-energy trauma; the second peak occurs in females in the seventh decade and is associated with low velocity falls. Trauma, increasing age, and osteoporosis are known risk factors [3-6].

This patient presents with severe arm pain in area of the mid-arm. Shortening of the upper arm suggests the presence of significant humeral shaft displacement. Evaluation of midshaft humerus fractures includes a detailed neurovascular exam of the affected arm. The radial nerve is most commonly injured by midshaft humerus fractures [1,4-6].

Fractures of the humeral shaft can be spiral, oblique or transverse. There are absolute and relative indications for surgical treatment.

Patients and Methods

We are reporting different cases of operative treatment of traumatic fractures of humeral shaft including operative treatment by means of external fixation, intramedullary fixation with long humeral nailing, intramedullary fixation with Rush nail and plate osteosynthesis.

A study represents patients with closed midshaft humerus fractures who were treated in emergency room.

Radiographs of the humeral shaft in an anteroposterior and lateral plane were necessary to evaluate the amount of angulation or displacement of fracture.

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Radiographs should include shoulder and elbow joints as well.

After evaluation of anatomy and biology of the fractures and background of the patient and capabilities of further home care here are some cases we treated in a certain way with overall good bone healing status, postoperative local status, neurocirculatory status, postoperative physical therapy course and overall functional results of injured limb and good patient satisfaction (Figures 1-6).

Results

Follow-up is initiated on a biweekly basis until radiographic and clinical union has occurred. Typical time for hard callus forming was 6 to 8 weeks.

In this study, no complications associated with humeral shaft fractures such as neurovascular compromise and

Figure 1 Transverse fracture of humeral shaft at 50-year old male patient, terminal faze of malignant disease not associated with fracture, injury by heavy blow to the arm by attacker; treated with intramedullary long humeral fixation with x-ray on day of injury, postoperative x-ray and 6 weeks after surgery with satisfactory healing, local status and patient satisfaction.

Figure 2 Transverse fracture of humeral shaft and middle of clavicle sustained by falling on the side of the body after transient ischemic brain stroke at 75 year old male patient treated immediatly with intramedullary fixation by means of Rush nail with x-ray on day of injury, postoperative x-ray and 6 weeks after surgery with satisfactory healing, local status and patient satisfaction.

Figure 3 Transverse fracture of humeral shaft at 37-year old male politraumatized patient treatet with intramedullary long humeral fixation with x-ray on day of injury, postoperative x-ray and 6 weeks after surgery with satisfactory healing, local status and patient satisfaction.

Figure 4 Transverse open fracture of humeral shaft at 75-year old female patient treated with external humeral fixation, fall on the steps after hearth attack, treated on day of injury with external fixation that was continued; x-ray on day of injury, postoperative x-ray and 6 weeks after surgery with satisfactory healing, local status and patient satisfaction.

nonunion were recorded. Radial nerve injury, the most common neurological complication of humeral shaft fracture that occurs in 11% of midshaft fractures didn't occur [7,8].

There was no evidence of nonunion of humeral shaft fractures. All fractures healed without infection.

Dicsussion

Several options are used for the management of humeral shaft fractures; conservative management, open Reduction and Internal Fixation (ORIF) with a plate, or closed reduction and Intramedullary Nailing (IMN). External fixator is also option, Most humeral shaft fractures has to be treated surgically; only small percent require functional bracing or hanging casts [9]. Today, there is an increased tendency to choose surgical management of humeral shaft fracture.The

Figure 5 Transverse fracture of humeral shaft at 73-year old female patient with alcohol abusive patient treated with external fixation with X-ray on day of injury, x-ray with applied intramedullary Rush nail humeral fixation further to external fixation not as a rule but as a necessity due to low compliance of the patient. Interesting method for an overall interesting patient.

Figure 6 Fragmented fracture of humeral shaft as a sports injury by fall at 18-year old patient treated with open reduction and plate osteosynthesis. x-ray on day of injury, postoperative x-ray and 6 weeks after surgery with satisfactory healing, local status and patient satisfaction. The patient returned to full sport activities within 6 months.

trend towards a more operative approach could be explained by the increased demand of patients and achievement of earlier immobilization.

It is generally accepted that acute, closed, uncomplicated fractures of the humeral diaphysis that occur in ambulatory, co-operative patients have high rates of union with good functional results, if treated nonoperatively. However, as for any treatment, the indications and contraindications for applying nonoperative treatment in fractures of the humeral diaphysis are constantly reviewed and subject to change, as surgical techniques are improving and the socioeconomic environment favors treatment options that can offer a faster recovery and earlier return to normal activities. Innovations in surgical techniques also play an important role.

Open reduction and internal fixation with a plate includes a 4.5 mm plate that should cover a minimum of six cortices above and below the fracture site [10]. This open operative technique allows a radial nerve identification and protection. For elderly patients, when faced with poor bone quality, there is smaller biomechanical benefit.

Intramedullary nailing can offer biomechanical and surgical advantages over plating. It allows lower bending forces and better load sharing [7,11]. Patterns in which intramedullary nailing has been found to be superior are pathological and impending fractures, segmental lesions and fractures in osteopenic bone. A simple middle transverse fracture is also a good indication for intramedullary nailing. Nail inserted through a smaller incision, allows for less soft tissue stripping compared to plating techniques.

There are many studies comparing intramedullary nailing and plating outcomes for humeral shaft fractures. One study comparing modern locking nails with direct compression plating, found no significant difference regarding union rates and functional outcomes [12]. This and some other studies recorded a higher complication rate after nailing, such as shoulder impingement, restriction of shoulder movement and need for hardware removal associated with nailing [13,14]. No significant differences regarding infection, nonunion, radial nerve injury and implant failure were noticed.

External fixation is an option in cases such as polytrauma patients with severe soft tissue damage, open contaminated fracture and associated vascular injury [15-17]. Studies reporting external fixators outcomes are rare.

In our study, we showed excellent results regarding external fixator humeral shaft fracture treatment. The union rate in patients with humeral shaft fractures using external fixator was the same as in other groups.

Healing of a mid-shaft humerus fracture with surgically management shorten healing times and improve alignment compared to non-surgically treatment [5].

Invasive bridge plating through an anterior incision with functional bracing in 110 patients reported a nonunion rate of 0 % for the surgical group versus 15% for the bracing group [18].

A randomized trial involving 60 patients comparing ORIF compression plating with functional bracing reported a shorter time in union in those treated with ORIF (13.9 versus 18.7 weeks) [5,19].

Bone healing is usually divided into three slightly overlapping stages; inflammatory, reparative, and remodeling [20-23]. It is difficult to provide an approximate time frame for each phase because healing rates vary widely according to age and comorbidities. Initially callus formation is cartilaginous, clinical union may occur before evidence of radiographic union is appreciable on radiographs. Clinical union classically marks the end of the reparative phase of fracture healing.

Some conditions impair fracture healing rates such as patient age, comorbidities, diabetes mellitus, arteriovascular disease, anemia, hypothyroidism, malnutrition, excessive

chronic alcohol and tobacco use. Some medications impair fracture healing [24]. Our study showed no difference among patients. Health status and age showed no difference in bone healing.

Plain radiographs are sufficient to confirm the diagnosis and plan the treatment for humeral shaft fractures. Anteroposterior and lateral radiographs are required to visualize and make a full assessment of the fracture.

In our cases, there was no difference concerning functional outcomes between different operative and surgical management for humeral shaft fractures. Therefore, an humeral shaft fracture is proper indication for operative and surgical management.

Most cases of fixation failure can be attributed to poor technique such as too a short plate, but biomechanical studies showed that a plate restore excellent bending and torsional stiffness to the humerus [25–28].

Competent fracture care requires a basic knowledge of bone biology and healing. Practical understanding and managing fractures is necessary.

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